

TRANSNATURE

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Definitions and Glossary

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1 Transboundary Biodiversity Protection: a definition

Biodiversity¹ is an encompassing term that includes ecosystems and their natural components as well as their interactions. Biodiversity is inherently borderless and does not stop at man-made frontiers – which follow the logic of power and the course of history, rather than ecological criteria. When ecosystems and their natural components are not enclosed within national boundaries nor subjected to the jurisdiction of a single State, they can be characterised as *transboundary and shared*.²

The attributes “transboundary” and “shared” have been accompanying the concept of specific ecosystems and natural resources³ more than that of biodiversity itself. Although the notion of “transboundary biodiversity” is frequently used in the literature, it has not been defined as such. This definition seems unnecessary for the borderless character of biodiversity, and thus the “transboundary” attribute is meant to define the governance, conservation or sustainable management of biodiversity.⁴ If defining “transboundary biodiversity” can be considered a needless tautological effort, clarifying what we mean with “transboundary biodiversity protection” is useful to set a common basis and inform the research objectives of the TRANSNATURE project.

Transboundary biodiversity protection entails the presence of cross-border cooperation explicitly aimed at ensuring the conservation of shared ecosystems or natural resources, and can be pursued together with other objectives. This express reference to conservation is one of the three elements relevant in all the cases selected in this project together with (2) the transboundary dimension of the governance arrangements considered, and (3) the presence of a plurality of authorities operating at different governance levels and cooperating in the case study area.

¹ According to Art. 2 of the Convention on Biological Diversity, this means “the variability among living organisms from all sources including, inter alia, terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part: this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems”.

² For Perrez “The term shared resources is typically used for resources which are on or straddle national boundaries and thus fall under the jurisdiction of more than one state”. Franz X Perrez, *Cooperative Sovereignty: From Independence to Interdependence in the Structure of International Environmental Law* (Brill Book Archive Part 1, ISBN: 9789004472495, Brill | Nijhoff 2000), p. 300.

³ Several international environmental regimes address the conservation and sustainable management of specific transboundary ecosystems or natural resources, for example, the Convention on Wetlands of International Importance especially as Waterfowl Habitat (1971, see Art. 5), the Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals (1979), the Convention on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Watercourses and International Lakes (1992), the Convention on the Law of Non-navigational Uses of International Watercourses (1997), Draft Articles on the Law of Transboundary Aquifers (2008). Based on the abovementioned regimes, specific bilateral and multilateral agreements have been adopted to jointly protect and manage transboundary/shared natural resources. The relevance of the notion of transboundary/shared natural resources emerges also from the literature. See, among others, Eyal Benvenisti, *Sharing Transboundary Resources: International Law and Optimal Resource Use* (Cambridge Studies in International and Comparative Law, Cambridge University Press 2002); Nadia Sánchez Castillo, ‘Differentiating between Sovereignty over Exclusive and Shared Resources in the Light of Future Discussions on the Law of Transboundary Aquifers’ (2015) 24(1) Rev Euro Comp & Int Env Law 4.

⁴ For instance, see Michelle Lim, ‘Governance criteria for effective transboundary biodiversity conservation’ (2016) 16(6) Int Environ Agreements 797, Maja Vasilijević and others, *Transboundary conservation: A systematic and integrated approach* (International Union for Conservation of Nature 2015), Louis J Kotzé and Thilo Marauhn (eds), *Transboundary governance of biodiversity* (Legal aspects of sustainable development, 1875-0923 volume 19, Brill Nijhoff 2014).

For the specific use of the term ‘transboundary biodiversity protection/conservation’ in the TRANSNATURE project, the following disclaimers are agreed:

- There is a stratification of governance and cooperation structures (‘plurality of authorities’ *supra*) that apply to the transboundary conservation area. The governance structures need to show different layers of authority that aim at the joined conservation of biodiversity in the area. As example, this means that the availability of a national management plan of each of the bordering countries as such is not sufficient; rather case studies do require a ‘joint’ management plan or a management scheme where both countries participate and cooperate in the management and implementation of conservation through different government layers and other layers of institutions or stakeholders also on a regional, European, or international scale.
- There should be an integration of transboundary elements with a focus on biodiversity (such as cooperation in the permitting process or inspection), that go beyond a mere formal and passive application of the existing transboundary cooperation duties, with limited to no added value in the field of conservation, such as those established by the Espoo Convention and the Aarhus Convention. Finding out if transboundary cooperation goes beyond the combination of existing schemes or if existing schemes contribute to a new form of governance is at the core of the project.
- The case studies apply to a defined area. This requirement relates to the broad application of certain impacts, such as of CO₂, pollution, effects of economic activities and others. The delineation of areas can be based on agreed borders (e.g. of protected areas), described ecosystems or population (e.g. wolves), and will be defined in accordance with the stakeholders of each study area.
- Transboundary projects have to demonstrate a causal link between the source of pollution and the impact-site. In other words, the environmental stressors need to be located in the research area. This means that a single focus on CO₂ emission is excluded: while all CO₂ emission contributes to the GHG-effect, it is difficult to establish a causal link between a specific CO₂-emission in the research area and the damage caused. Case studies, however, could consider local sources of pollution, such as relating to groundwater or nitrogen deposition, where a causal link with the area can be established. Also, cases where an accumulation of small impacts lead to significant damage can be taken into account if a causal link can be established (see definition of cumulative effects below).

This general definition can be better fine-tuned in each case study since cooperation is not an on-off button but varies significantly depending on the context considered. To this purpose a set of scales will enable to further clarify to what extent transboundary biodiversity protection is pursued and, potentially, achieved in each case study. The scales are the following:

1. Focus of cooperation: from specific species to an entire ecosystem;
2. Cooperation priority: from sustainable management to conservation;
3. Conservation objective: from maintaining the status quo to landscape restoration;
4. Shared geographical delineation: is there a shared definition/description of the area subjected to cooperation or is its delineation indirectly emerging from the territorial competences of the authorities involved in the cooperation scheme?
5. Type of cooperative instrument in place (binding agreement as per international/national law, soft law instrument, declaration, etc.);
6. Evidence of concrete implementation (joint measures, action plan, joint institutions, etc.);
7. Institutional aspect: number of actors involved in the relevant area and their governance level (only governmental actors, local authorities, other stakeholders, etc.);
8. Participatory tools foreseen (community bodies, procedural elements, etc.) and level of public participation;
9. Governance structure: innovative in comparison to traditional protected areas or other international agreements (i.e. bilateral river commission, CMS-based agreement, etc.);
10. Innovation in terms of conservation objectives pursued, if beyond targets agreed in EU legal instruments or in international environmental treaties;
11. The inclusion of reactive or proactive biodiversity conservation objectives in the cooperation scheme;
12. Integration/harmonisation of national permitting schemes (if relevant, as for water use);
13. Wildlife crime: if mentioned;
14. Pollution: specific sources covered;
15. Others.

2 Glossary

Biodiversity: “the variability among living organisms from all sources including, inter alia, terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems” (CBD, art. 2).

Conservation (of biodiversity): any activity aimed at the in-situ maintenance and recovery of ecosystems and natural habitats as well as of viable populations of species in their natural surroundings.

Conservation status of a natural habitat [adapted from Habitats Directive art. 1(e)]: the sum of the influences acting on a natural habitat and its typical species that might affect its long-term natural distribution, structure, and function as well as the long-term survival of its typical species in the relevant territory. The status is defined as ‘favourable’ when:

- its natural range and areas it covers within that range are stable or increasing, and
- the specific structure and functions which are necessary for its long-term maintenance exist for the foreseeable future, and
- the conservation status of its typical species is favourable (as defined below).

Conservation status of a species [adapted from Habitats Directive art. 1(i)]: the sum of the influences acting on the species concerned that may affect the long-term distribution and abundance of its population in the relevant territory. The status is defined as ‘favourable’ when:

- Population dynamics data on the species concerned indicate that it is maintaining itself a long-term basis as a viable component of its natural habitat, and
- the natural range of the species is neither being reduced nor is likely to be reduced for the foreseeable future, and
- There is, and will probably continue to be, a sufficiently large habitat to maintain its populations on a long-term basis.

Cross-border/transboundary/transfrontier are used as synonyms to indicate governance dynamics that happen across national boundaries and involve actors or authorities (local/regional/national/supranational) of two or more States.

Cumulative effects consist in “the impact on the environment which results from the incremental impact of [an] action when added to other past, present, and reasonably foreseeable future actions regardless of what agency ... or person undertakes such other actions”.⁵

Ecosystem: a dynamic complex of plant, animal and micro-organism communities and their non-living environment interacting as a functional unit (CBD, art. 2). Ecosystem can refer to any functioning unit at any scale (CBD/COP/5/23).

⁵ Great Barrier Reef Region Strategic Assessment: Strategic Assessment Report 2014 (Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority), 1-7.

Ecosystem approach: a strategy for the integrated management of land, water and living resources that promotes the conservation and sustainable use in an equitable way (CBD/COP/5/23). It recognizes that humans, with their cultural diversity, are an integral component of many ecosystems (CBD/COP/7/11). Key elements are: a holistic approach to conservation (going beyond individual and distinct species and habitats); the balancing of conservation with human needs; decentralization of management mechanisms (CBD/COP/5/6).⁶

Governance can refer to how society defines its goals and priorities: the processes used to take decisions and implement them, the actors involved, and the structures set in place to this end. It relates to the interactions among the legislative, institutional, and political frameworks operating in a specific context and relevant for society's goals and priorities. Therefore, governance of natural resources encompasses the conservation and development objectives connected to such resources, the institutional structure useful to achieve them, the relevant legal and political orders, the actors involved in decision-making and implementation of decisions as well as management activities.⁷

Participation is intended as public participation in environmental matters and encompasses access to information, participation in decision-making, and access to administrative and judicial remedies, as conceptualized in the 1998 UNECE Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters (so-called Aarhus Convention). This Convention distinguishes between the (general) public and the public concerned: the former includes all actors outside the governmental administration (Art. 2(4)), while the latter refers to a more restricted group of subjects that are "affected or likely to be affected by, or have an interest in, environmental decision-making" (Art. 2(5)). Both the public and the public concerned can actively be engaged in transboundary cooperation efforts – like those studied in TRANSNATURE – through diverse mechanisms and with different degrees of involvement (formal and informal). Participation does not equal cooperation but can contribute to it.

Pollution: means the direct or indirect introduction, as a result of human activity, of substances, vibrations, heat or noise into air, water or land which may be harmful to human health or the quality of the environment, result in damage to material property, or impair or interfere with amenities and other legitimate uses of the environment.⁸

Protection (of biodiversity): combines conservation activities and the sustainable use of natural components, and thus responds to the application of the first two objectives of the CBD.

Stakeholders encompass all the actors interested in and involved in transboundary cooperation in the project sites. These actors belong to the different governance levels and sectors relevant for each site. They can have a more or less formal role in the cooperation (for instance, as representatives of transboundary/national/regional/local authorities or civil society organisations), a "procedural" role when guiding the cooperation dynamic and/or participate to represent their own interests (as in the case of specific sectors/interests: tourism, mining, hunting, fishing etc.)

Sustainable use: the use of components of biological diversity in a way and at a rate that does not lead to the long-term decline of biological diversity, thereby maintaining its potential to meet the needs and aspirations of present and future generations (CBD, art. 2).

⁶ See pp 95-96 and 98 T. Maruhn and A-M Böhringer, in Kotzé and Maruhn (eds.) 2014; see also p 1225 Harro van Asselt, 'Managing the fragmentation of international environmental law: Forests at the intersection of the climate and biodiversity regimes' (2012) 44 International Law and Politics 1205.

⁷ Emma Mitrotta, 'Decentralised International Cooperation: Enhancing Conservation and Sustainable Management of Transboundary Natural Resources' (PhD Thesis, University of Trento 2019), 8.

⁸ Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control).

Transboundary natural resources: any element coming from nature that is on or straddle national boundaries and thus falls under the jurisdiction of more than one state.

Transboundary pollution: pollution whose physical origin is situated wholly or in part within the area under the jurisdiction of one [state] and which has adverse effects, other than effects of a global nature, in the area under the jurisdiction of [another state].⁹

Wildlife crime means any criminal or administrative offence related to:

- (1) the killing, destruction, taking of, possession, sale or offering for sale of a specimen or specimens of wild fauna or flora species listed in Annexes IV or V (when species in Annex V are subject to the same measures as those adopted for species in Annex IV) to Council Directive 92/43/EEC and the species referred to in Article 1 of Directive 2009/147/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council;
- (2) trading in specimens of wild fauna or flora species or parts or derivatives thereof listed in Annexes A and B to Council Regulation (EC) No 338/97, and imports of specimens of such species, parts or derivatives thereof listed in Annex C of that Regulation;
- (3) any conduct which causes the deterioration of a habitat, or the disturbance of animal species listed in Annex II (a) of Council Directive 92/43/EEC, within a protected site, within the meaning of Article 6(2) of that Directive. Habitat within a protected site means any habitat of species for which an area is classified as a special protection area pursuant to Article 4(1) or (2) of Directive 2009/147/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, or any natural habitat or habitat of species for which a site is designated as a special area of conservation in accordance with Article 4(4) of Council Directive 92/43/EEC or for which a site is listed as site of Community importance in accordance with Article 4(2) of Council Directive 92/43/EEC.

3 References

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⁹ Agreement between the Government of the United States and the Government of Canada on Air Quality, (Ottawa) 13 March 1991, in force 13 March 1991, 1852 UNTS 80.

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